

thus resulting in a neutral complex. The electronic spectrum (in nujol mull) shows bands at 18.5 kK and 20 kK. No other electronic transitions are observed below 10 kK. Square planar stereochemistry is thus suggested for the red nickel(II) complex⁸. Due to its extreme insolubility in common organic solvents, conductance measurements was not feasible. The yellowish-green nickel(II) complex shows three bands at 10.26, 16.0 and 26.3 kK. These bands are assignable to ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (ν_2), ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The ratio of $\nu_3 : \nu_1$ is 1.56 indicating an octahedral environment⁹ around the metal ion. There are also two weak bands at 18.52 and 20 kK. These are assigned to the two spin forbidden transitions ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ and ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$, respectively. From the transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 , we get $10 Dq = 10.26 \text{ kK}$; $B' = 910 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\beta = 0.87$ (free ion B value = 1041 cm^{-1}). Bivalent electrolytic nature of the yellowish-green nickel(II) complex is indicated by the molar conductance ($\Delta_M = 157 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in methanol¹⁰. Magnetic moment value ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.16 \text{ B.M.}$) also lends support to an octahedral configuration.

The mass spectrum of the red diamagnetic complex (I) clearly shows the parent ion (m/e) peak at 584 (monomer molecular weight 584.17).

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Stabilisation of Salicylidene Amino Acids by Magnesium(II)

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THE salicylideneamino acid Schiff bases (I) are known to be unstable enough in the absence of a suitable metal ion¹. Quite stable complexes of these ligands with copper(II)², nickel(II)³, cobalt(II)⁴, manganese(II)⁵, (III)⁶ and zinc(II)^{7,8} are well established. The enhanced stability has been ascribed to the two chelate rings at the metal ion¹. We now report that a similar stabilisation effect has been observed in the presence of magnesium(II). Very few magnesium(II) complexes with tridentate ligands are known. A survey reveals the characterisation of six-coordinate magnesium(II) complexes with tridentate Schiff bases, acetylaceton-1-amidino-O-alkylurea⁹ and salicylidene aroyl (heteroaroyl) hydrazones⁹. The Schiff bases stabilised in the present investigation are salicylidene-glycine [salglyH₂] (I) and salicylidene- α -alanine [sal- α -alanH₂].

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Results and Discussion

A report⁵ from this laboratory on the manganese(II) complexes of a large number of salicylidene amino acids has established that the complexes possess *trans* aquo- μ -bis(salicylidene amino-acidato)-di-manganese(II) structure(II). Dimeric structures have been authenticated for nickel(II)⁸ and cobalt(II)⁴ from a scrutiny of the magnetic moments and electronic spectra of their complexes. Since magnesium(II) offers no special magnetic and electronic spectral properties, we had to decide on the nature of the present complexes on the basis of a comparison of the infrared spectra of the magnesium(II) complex with those of the nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes. These spectra are very nearly superimposable. All these complexes are characterised by a broad strong absorption in the region 3200–3400 cm^{-1} standing for $\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$. The strong band at $\sim 1660 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a medium band at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to coordinated $\nu(\text{COO})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹⁰. The band at $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ favours a strong binding of the metal ion with the phenolic oxygen¹¹. Table 1 shows all the bands of $[\text{Mg}(\text{salgly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$ and $[\text{Mg}(\text{sal-}\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$.

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRAL BANDS OF $[\text{Mg}(\text{salgly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$ AND $[\text{Mg}(\text{sal-}\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$

Complex	$\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$
$[\text{Mg}(\text{salgly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$	3400-3200bs, 1660s, 1600m, 1540m, 1475s, 1445s, 1410s, 1340s, 1309s, 1198s, 1155s, 1132s, 1085s, 1042m, 1020m, 958m, 950w, 905s, 858w, 770s, 760s, 750s.
$[\text{Mg}(\text{sal-}\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$	3400-3200bs, 1665s, 1600m, 1570m, 1540m, 1470s, 1450sh, 1400s, 1345s, 1300s, 1198s, 1155sh, 1130s, 1080w, 1040w, 1010w, 960w, 900s, 860m, 770sh, 750s.

bs = broad, strong ; s = strong ; sh = shoulder ; m = medium and w = weak.

Thermogravimetric analyses of the complexes also have profiles comparable to those of nickel(II), cobalt(II) and manganese(II). The coordinated water is lost over two slightly overlapping steps—one over the range ~ 50 to 200° and the other over 200 to 250° . The final thermal decomposition to MgO occurs over the range 400 to 600° .

(Total loss. Found : 83.3. Calcd. 83.0%)

(Total loss. Found : 84.4. Calcd. 84.0%)

The intermediate dimeric square planar species $[\text{Mg}(\text{salgly})]_2$ and $[\text{Mg}(\text{sal-}\alpha\text{-alan})]_2$ (III) appear to have a range of stability ($250-400^\circ$).

Successful syntheses of the magnesium(II) complexes of the salicylideneamino acid ligands further substantiate our earlier assertion⁵ that such syntheses are not dictated by CFSE [cf. octahedral CFSE of Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Mn(III) (all high spin), Zn(II) and Mg(II) : -12 Dq , -8 Dq , 0 Dq , -6 Dq , 0 Dq and 0 Dq].

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (0.5 g) was taken in ethanol (10 ml) and heated on a steam bath. A hot aqueous solution of glycine (0.35 g in 5 ml) was added and refluxed for about 15 min. Magnesium acetate tetrahydrate (0.85 g) in ethanol (10 ml) was then added to the above solution and refluxing continued for some time. The light yellow crystals were collected, washed first with water and then with ethanol and dried in air. (Found : Mg, 10.4 ; N, 6.1. Calcd. for $[\text{Mg}(\text{salgly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$; Mg, 10.1 ; N, 5.9%). The salicylidene- α -alanine complex was also obtained as above using α -alanine instead of glycine. (Found : Mg, 9.8 ; N, 5.6. Calcd. for $[\text{Mg}(\text{sal-}\alpha\text{-alan})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$; Mg, 9.5 ; N, 5.9%). Thermal analyses, as given above, also support such formulation.

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